

PhenoBR: a model to phenotype body condition dynamics in meat sheep

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Supplementary hypothesis S1

For productive cycle 1, if t_b is not included between days 0 and 160 (i.e. approximately between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 160 and 330 (i.e. approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- If no BCS maximum found, then $t_b=0$;
- If no BCS minimum were found between days 160 and 330 but there is a BCS minimum before day 330 then $t_e=\text{day where BCS is minimal}$;
- If no BCS minimum found, then $t_e=360$;
- If two minimums found during the perturbation time, then $t_e= \text{day where BCS is minimal}$.

For productive cycle 2, if t_b is not included between days 360 and 520 (i.e. approximately between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 520 and 690 (i.e. approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- If no BCS maximum found between days 360 and 520 but there is a BCS maximum after day 520 then $t_b=\text{day where BCS is maximal}$;
- If no BCS minimum were found between days 520 and 690 but there is a BCS minimum before day 520 then $t_e= \text{day where BCS is minimal}$;
- If no BCS maximum found, then $t_b=360$;
- If no BCS minimum found, then $t_e=720$;
- If two BCS maximums found before the perturbation time, then $t_b = \text{day where BCS is maximal}$;
- If two minimums found during the perturbation time, then $t_e== \text{day where BCS is minimal}$.

For productive cycle 3, if t_b is not included between days 720 and 880 (i.e. approximately between mating and lambing days) and t_e is not included between days 880 and 1050 (i.e. approximately between lambing and post-weaning):

- If no BCS maximum found between days 720 and 880 but there is a BCS maximum before day 720 or after day 880 then $t_b= \text{day where BCS is maximal}$;

- If no BCS minimum found between days 880 and 1050 but there is a BCS minimum before day 880 then t_e = day where BCS is minimal;
- If no BCS minimum found, then t_e = 1050;
- If no BCS maximum found, then t_b = 720.

Some animals did not match the model correctly, so special conditions on the initial parameters were set up for them so that they would be better represented.

- $kb_1 = 0.001$ instead of 0.005 ; $kb_2 = 0.002$ instead of 0.003 and $kp_1 = 0.005$ instead of 0.003
- $kb_1 = 0.001$ instead of 0.005 ; $kb_2 = 0.001$ instead of 0.003 and $kp_1 = 0.005$ instead of 0.003
- For 3 animals, one value of BCS was deleted because of its physiological impossibility (value far too high or too low when compared with the other values of the same ewe)
- Four animals with only one parity and with less than 4 points in the cycle or between t_b and t_e were removed.

S1 code. SAS code for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt , example with lsmeans obtained for the variation factor cycle.

```
proc mixed data = interv_2 covtest;
class productive_cycle litter_size year age_first_lambing;
model kp = productive_cycle litter_size year age_first_lambing;
repeated productive_cycle / subject = animal type = cs ;
lsmeans productive_cycle / pdiff;
```

```
proc mixed data = interv_2 covtest;
class productive_cycle litter_size year age_first_lambing;
model kb = productive_cycle litter_size age_first_lambing;
repeated productive_cycle / subject = animal type = cs ;
lsmeans productive_cycle / pdiff;
```

```
proc mixed data = interv_2 covtest;
class cycle nweaned m_n_all;
model Dt = productive_cycle litter_size year age_first_lambing;
repeated productive_cycle / subject = animal type = cs ;
lsmeans productive_cycle / pdiff;
```

SAS code for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt , example with lsmeans obtained for the variation factor cluster BCS at cycle 1.

```
proc mixed data = cycle1 covtest;
class cluster_BCS litter_size year age_first_lambing;
model kp = cluster_BCS litter_size year age_first_lambing litter_size
* age_first_lambing litter_size * cluster_BCS;
```

```

lsmeans cluster_BCS /pdiff;
proc mixed data = cycle1 covtest;
class cluster_BCS litter_size year age_first_lambing;
model kb = cluster_BCS litter_size year age_first_lambing m_n_all * cluster_BCS;
lsmeans cluster_BCS /pdiff;

```

```

proc mixed data = cycle1 covtest;
class cluster_BCS litter_size year age_first_lambing;
model interv = cluster_BCS litter_size age_first_lambing;
lsmeans cluster_BCS /pdiff;

```

Table S1. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error) according to the productive cycle and significance of litter size, year and productive cycle x litter size interaction effects in ewes performing first lambing at 1 year old.

		k_p	k_b	Perturbation length (Δt)
n obs		1390	1390	1390
productive cycle	1	4.53 (0.17) a	2.92 (0.15) a	205.39 (7.89) a
	2	4.49 (0.06) a	2.96 (0.05) a	166.21 (2.40) b
	3	3.80 (0.09) b	2.96 (0.07) a	165.87 (3.89) b
	Sign.	***	NS	***
litter size	Sign.	***	***	NS
year	Sign.	***	***	***
productive cycle*litter size	Sign.	NS	NS (0.07)	**

n obs, Number of observations; k_p , Rate of body reserves mobilization; k_b , Rate of body reserves accretion; Δt , duration of body reserves mobilization period; Sign., Significance; NS, non-significant. Pvalue, *** < 0.001, ** < 0.01, * < 0.05 ; Values of LSmeans with different letters indicate significant differences between levels of each factor.

Table S2. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error) according to the productive cycle and significance of litter size, year and productive cycle x litter size interaction effects in ewes performing first lambing at 2 years old.

		k_p	k_b	Perturbation length (Δt)
n obs		1614	1614	1614
productive cycle	1	5.37 (0.11) a	3.48 (0.08) a	204.15 (3.76) a
	2	4.79 (0.12) b	3.15 (0.08) b	177.65 (3.96) b
	3	4.33 (0.13) c	2.69 (0.09) c	171.00 (4.65) b
	Sign.	***	***	***
litter size	Sign.	***	***	***
year	Sign.	***	***	***
productive cycle*litter size	Sign.	NS	NS	NS

n obs, Number of observations; k_p , Rate of body reserves mobilization; k_b , Rate of body reserves accretion; Δt , duration of body reserves mobilization period; Sign., Significance; NS, non-significant. Pvalue, *** < 0.001, ** < 0.01, * < 0.05 ; Values of LSmeans with different letters indicate significant differences between levels of each factor.

Table S3. Summary of least-squares means for the model parameters (standard error) according to the clusters of adjusted BCS

		n obs	k_p	k_b	Perturbation length
Productive cycle 1	BC10	1037	5.16 (0.13) a	3.33 (0.04) a	213.74 (1.85) a
	BC11	105	6.36 (0.20) b	2.90 (0.10) b	214.29 (4.94) a
	Sign.		***	***	NS
n obs		1069	1069	1069	
Productive cycle 2	BC12	822	4.80 (0.06) a	3.15 (0.04) a	176.65 (2.02) a
	BC13	247	4.96 (0.11) a	3.29 (0.08) a	166.45 (3.50) b
	Sign.		NS	NS	*
n obs		414	414	414	
Productive cycle 3	BC14	235	4.68 (0.12) a	2.98 (0.08) a	185.42 (3.71) a
	BC15	179	4.57 (0.12) a	3.02 (0.08) a	175.30 (3.79) b
	Sign.		NS	NS	*

n obs, Number of observations; Pvalue, *** < 0.001, * < 0.05; Sign., Significance; NS, non-significant.

Productive cycle 1:

- BC10: lowest BCS loss and BCS gain;
- BC11: highest BCS loss and BCS gain.

Productive cycle 2:

- BC12: lowest BCS loss and intermediate BCS gain;
- BC13: highest BCS loss and intermediate BCS gain.

Productive cycle 3:

- BC14: intermediate BCS loss and BCS gain;
- BC15: intermediate BCS loss and BCS gain

S1 Fig. Histogram of the objective function (f_{obj}). Only a limited number of ewes with $f_{obj} > 1$ could be observed.

S2 Fig. Scatter plot of the model parameters. Deviations from linearity can be observed, therefore Spearman method was used to calculate the correlation coefficients.

S3 Fig. Cluster profiles for the Body Condition Score (BCS) in Romane ewes over their production cycles 1 (at the top), 2 (in the middle) and 3 (at the bottom) (from Macé et al., 2018).

The scatter plot on the left of each graph represents the individual coordinates on the two first principal components of the functional principal component analysis. The textbox on the right of each graph indicates the proportion of animals in each cluster, which is given in percentage (%). ¹ The composition of each cluster at productive cycle i is given by indicating the proportion (%) of animals from clusters found at previous cycle $i-1$.

M, Mating; Pa, Early pregnancy; Pb, Mid-Pregnancy; L, Lambing; Sa, Beginning of suckling; Sb, End of suckling; W, Weaning; D, Dry-off; Adjusted BCS, BCS taking into account average individual BCS levels across cycles.

S4 Fig. Heteroscedasticity, QQ-Plots and distributions for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt

Residuals at cycle 1

S5 Fig. Heteroscedasticity, QQ-Plots and distributions for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt at cycle 1.

Residuals at cycle 2

S6 Fig. Heteroscedasticity, QQ-Plots and distributions for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt at cycle 2

Residuals at cycle 3

S7 Fig. Heteroscedasticity, QQ-Plots and distributions for model parameter's k_p , k_b and Δt at cycle 3